

Separation and Identification of Micro-quantities of Metallic Ions by Ring Oven Technique using Tartrate as a Complexant

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A simple microanalytical method for separation of metallic ions of the same group of qualitative analysis [Hg(I), Pb(II), Ag(I), Hg(II), Bi(III), Cu(II), Cd(II), As(III), Sb(III), and Sn(II)] with tartrate as complexing agent, using ring oven technique, has been studied. With the addition of the complexing agent, the separations improve with distinct separation zones, whereas in the absence of the same, no distinct separation is possible. The complete separation and identification of a group of elements can be made within five minutes.

It is well known that complex formation plays an important role in the separation of ions in filter paper chromatography, as pointed out by us in a previous paper (Singh and Dey, this *Journal*, 1961, 38, 193). We have also observed the variation in the migration of ions on filter paper strips in presence of tartrate as a complexant (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1959, 165, 81). Following the ring oven technique outlined by Weisz (*Microchim. Acta*, 1954, 140, 367, 787), we separated metal ions, with oxalate, citrate, and EDTA as complexants (unpublished). In this paper the separation of metallic ions of the same group, using tartrate as the complexant by the same technique, has been described.

EXPERIMENTAL

Weisz ring oven, manufactured by National Appliance Co., U.S.A., was used. The heating was done by connecting the leads of the apparatus through a dimmerstat (Automatic Electrical Devices, Bombay) giving 25 volts from 220 volts/50 cycles A.C. mains. The temperature of the heating block was 100°.

Procedure.—Standard solutions of nitrates of Pb(II), Hg(I), Ag(I), Cu(II), Hg(II), Cd(II), Bi(III), Co(III) and chlorides of Sb(III), Sn(II), As(III), and sodium tartrate (reagent grade chemicals) were prepared. Whatman filter No. 1 was used. 60% Ethanol was used as solvent. Ternary, quaternary, and pentanary mixtures, generally of the same group, containing equal concentrations of the metal solutions with varying proportions of sodium tartrate were prepared, keeping the total volume constant. The ratio of the total concentration of the metals (obtained by adding the concentrations in molarity of the metals) to the concentration of tartrate added, has been expressed as the metal tartrate ratio (equivalents of tartrate). A very small drop of the ternary, quaternary, and pentanary mixtures having a volume of 0.0035 c.c. was taken in a micropipette and dropped at the centre of the paper. This paper was placed on the cylindrical block and kept stationary with the help of the aluminium ring and dried by heating. The spot was treated three times by dropping the solvent through the capillary pipette, inserted into the guide tube of the ring oven. The chromatograms were dried on the ring oven and developed by means of suitable indicators. The sequence of ions mentioned in the following description refers to the position of the rings from the centre to the outer edge, as a result of separation.

In ternary, quaternary, and pentanary mixtures, the final concentrations of each of the metal ions were 0.033*M*, 0.025*M*, and 0.02*M* respectively.

Separation of Ag(I), Hg(I) and Pb(II).—The separation of these metal ions is possible up to the addition of 0.48 equivalents of the complexing agent. With higher concentrations of the same, no separation is possible. A good separation was obtained when 0.16 to 0.3

equivalents of the complexing agent were used. The sequence of separation is Hg(I)-Ag(I)-Pb(II). The chromatograms were marked when these were moist. A complete separation and identification of the first group elements can be made in four minutes.

Separation of Cu(II), Cd(II), and Hg(II).—No separation is possible without the addition of the complexing agent. The separation of Cu(II), Cd(II), and Hg(II) ions is obtained when 1 to 1.6 equivalents of the complexing agent are used. Beyond 1.6 equivalents of the same, separation is not possible due to spreading and overlapping of the zones. The sequence of separation is Cd(II)-Hg(II)-Cu(II).

Separation of Cu(II), Cd(II), and Bi(III).—In the separation of these ions, only Bi(III) ions could be separated by addition of tartrate as a complexing agent. The sequence of separation is Bi(III)-[Cu(II)-Cd(II)].

Separation of Cu(II), Cd(II), and Pb(II).—Only the separation of lead (II) is possible up to the addition of 0.80 equivalent of tartrate. It may be seen that a feeble separation is obtained when 1.0 to 1.6 equivalents of the complexing agent are used. The sequence of separation is Pb(II)-[Cu(II)-Cd(II)]. This separation is not sharp due to spreading of copper (II) and cadmium (II) zones.

Separation of Cu(II), Cd(II), Pb(II), and Hg(II).—No sharp separation of the metallic ions is possible under the experimental conditions due to the spreading of the zones. The sequence of separation, however, is found to be [Pb(II)-Hg(II)]-Cd(II)-Cu(II) up to the addition of 0.36 equivalents of tartrate and with higher concentration of the same, no separation occurs. With the addition of 0.48 or more equivalents of the complexing agent, most of the Cu(II) ions do not move from the initial spot.

Separation of Cu(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), Pb(II), and Co(II).—No satisfactory separation of ions is possible with tartrate as complexing agent due to spreading and overlapping of zones.

Separation of As(III), Sb(III), and Sn(II).—The separation was effected up to the addition of 0.96 equivalents of tartrate. With higher concentration of the same, the separation was not possible. The sequence of separation is Sb(III)-As(III)-Sn(II). The complete separation and identification of second B group elements can be made in four minutes.

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